

Top Download Article in Computer Science & Information Technology Research: October 2020

**International Journal of Computer Science and
Information Technology (IJCSIT)**

Google Scholar Citation

Cited by

[VIEW ALL](#)

	All	Since 2015
Citations	7758	5907
h-index	44	34
i10-index	198	169

ISSN: 0975-3826(online); 0975-4660 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijsit.html>

SECURITY THREATS ON CLOUD COMPUTING VULNERABILITIES

Te-Shun Chou

**Department of Technology Systems, East Carolina University, Greenville,
NC, U.S.A.**

ABSTRACT

Clouds provide a powerful computing platform that enables individuals and organizations to perform variety levels of tasks such as: use of online storage space, adoption of business applications, development of customized computer software, and creation of a “realistic” network environment. In previous years, the number of people using cloud services has dramatically increased and lots of data has been stored in cloud computing environments. In the meantime, data breaches to cloud services are also increasing every year due to hackers who are always trying to exploit the security vulnerabilities of the architecture of cloud. In this paper, three cloud service models were compared; cloud security risks and threats were investigated based on the nature of the cloud service models. Real world cloud attacks were included to demonstrate the techniques that hackers used against cloud computing systems. In addition, countermeasures to cloud security breaches are presented.

KEYWORDS

Cloud computing, cloud security threats and countermeasures, cloud service models

For More Details : <https://airconline.com/ijcsit/V11N6/11619ijcsit04.pdf>

Volume Link : http://aircse.org/journal/ijcsit2019_curr.html

REFERENCES

1. DataLossDB Open Security Foundation. <http://datalossdb.org/statistics>
2. Sophos Security Threat Report 2012. <http://www.sophos.com/>
3. Amazon.com Server Said to Have Been Used in Sony Attack, May 2011. <http://www.bloomberg.com/news/2011-05-13/sony-network-said-to-have-been-invaded-by-hackers-using-amazon-com-server.html>
4. D. Jamil and H. Zaki, "[Security Issues in Cloud Computing and Countermeasures](#)," International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology, Vol. 3 No. 4, pp. 2672- 2676, April 2011.
5. K. Zunnurhain and S. Vrbsky, "[Security Attacks and Solutions in Clouds](#)," 2nd IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing Technology and Science, Indianapolis, December 2010.
6. W. A. Jansen, "Cloud Hooks: Security and Privacy Issues in Cloud Computing," 44th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, pp. 1–10, Koloa, Hawaii, January 2011.
7. T. Roth, "[Breaking Encryptions Using GPU Accelerated Cloud Instances](#)," Black Hat Technical Security Conference, 2011.
8. CERT Coordination Center, Denial of Service. http://www.packetstormsecurity.org/distributed/denial_of_service.html
9. M. Jensen, J. Schwenk, N. Gruschka, and L. L. Iacono, "[On Technical Security Issues in Cloud Computing](#)," IEEE International Conference in Cloud Computing, pp. 109-116, Bangalore, 2009.
10. Thunder in the Cloud: \$6 Cloud-Based Denial-of-Service Attack, August 2010. http://blogs.computerworld.com/16708/thunder_in_the_cloud_6_cloud_based_denial_of_service_attack
11. DDoS Attack Rains Down on Amazon Cloud, October 2009. http://www.theregister.co.uk/2009/10/05/amazon_bitbucket_outage/
12. 2011 CyberSecurity Watch Survey, CERT Coordination Center at Carnegie Mellon University.
13. D. Catteddu and G. Hogben, "[Cloud Computing Benefits, Risks and Recommendations for Information Security](#)," The European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA), November 2009.

14. Insider Threats Related to Cloud Computing, CERT, July 2012. <http://www.cert.org/>
15. Data Breach Trends & Stats, Symantec, 2012. <http://www.indefenseofdata.com/data-breach-trendsstats/>
16. 2012 Has Delivered Her First Giant Data Breach, January 2012. <http://www.infosecisland.com/blogview/19432-2012-Has-Delivered-Her-First-Giant-DataBreach.html>
17. A Few Wrinkles Are Etching Facebook, Other Social Sites, USA Today, 2011. http://www.usatoday.com/printedition/life/20090115/socialnetworking15_st.art.html
18. An Update on LinkedIn Member Passwords Compromised, LinkedIn Blog, June, 2012. <http://blog.linkedin.com/2012/06/06/linkedin-member-passwords-compromised/>
19. Dropbox: Yes, We Were Hacked, August 2012. <http://gigaom.com/cloud/dropbox-yes-we-werehacked/>
20. Web Based Attacks, Symantec White Paper, February 2009.
21. Symantec Internet Security Threat Report, 2011 Trends, Vol. 17, April 2012.
22. P. P. Ramgonda and R. R. Mudholkar, "[Cloud Market Cogitation and Techniques to Averting SQL Injection for University Cloud](#)," International Journal of Computer Technology and Applications, Vol. 3, No. 3, pp. 1217-1224, January, 2012.
23. A. S. Choudhary and M. L. Dhore, "[CIDT: Detection of Malicious Code Injection Attacks on Web Application](#)," International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 52, No. 2, pp. 19-26, August 2012.
24. Web Application Attack Report For The Second Quarter of 2012. <http://www.firehost.com/company/newsroom/web-application-attack-report-second-quarter-2012>
25. Visitors to Sony PlayStation Website at Risk of Malware Infection, July 2008. <http://www.sophos.com/en-us/press-office/press-releases/2008/07/playstation.aspx>
26. N. Provos, M. A. Rajab, and P. Mavrommatis, "Cybercrime 2.0: When the Cloud Turns Dark," ACM Communications, Vol. 52, No. 4, pp. 42–47, 2009.
27. S. S. Rajan, Cloud Security Series | SQL Injection and SaaS, Cloud Computing Journal, November 2010.

28. Researchers Demo Cloud Security Issue With Amazon AWS Attack, October 2011. http://www.pcworld.idg.com.au/article/405419/researchers_demo_cloud_security_is_sue_amazon_aws_attack/
29. M. McIntosh and P. Austel, "XML Signature Element Wrapping Attacks and Countermeasures," 2005 workshop on Secure web services, ACM Press, New York, NY, pp. 20–27, 2005.
30. N. Gruschka and L. L. Iacono, "[Vulnerable Cloud: SOAP Message Security Validation Revisited](#)," IEEE International Conference on Web Services, Los Angeles, 2009.
31. A. Tripathi and A. Mishra, "Cloud Computing Security Considerations Interface," 2011 IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Communications and Computing, Xi'an, China, September 2011.
32. H. C. Li, P. H. Liang, J. M. Yang, and S. J. Chen, "Analysis on Cloud-Based Security Vulnerability Assessment," IEEE International Conference on E-Business Engineering, pp.490-494, November 2010.
33. Amazon:Hey Spammers, Get Off My Cloud!http://voices.washingtonpost.com/securityfix/2008/07/amazon_hey_spammers_get_off_my.html
34. W. Jansen and T. Grance, "Guidelines on Security and Privacy in Public Cloud Computing," Computer Security Division, Information Technology Laboratory, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Special Publication 800-144, December 2011.
35. Tackling the Insider Threat <http://www.bankinfosecurity.com/blogs.php?postID=140>
36. "Cloud Security Risks and Solutions," White Paper, BalaBit IT Security, July 2010.
37. S. J. Stolfo, M. B. Salem, and A. D. Keromytis, "Fog computing: Mitigating Insider Data Theft Attacks in the Cloud," IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy Workshops, pp. 125-128, San Francisco, CA, 2012.
38. M. Jensen, C. Meyer, J. Somorovsky, and J. Schwenk, "On the Effectiveness of XML Schema Validation for Countering XML Signature Wrapping Attacks," First International Workshop on Securing Services on the Cloud, Milan, Italy, September 2011.
39. S. Gajek, M. Jensen, L. Liao, and J. Schwenk, "Analysis of Signature Wrapping Attacks and Countermeasures," IEEE International Conference on Web Services, pp. 575–582, Miami, Florida, July 2009.

DATA WAREHOUSE AND BIG DATA INTEGRATION

**Sonia Ordoñez Salinas and Alba Consuelo Nieto Lemus Faculty of Engineering,
Distrial F.J.C University, Bogotá, Colombia**

ABSTRACT

Big Data triggered furthered an influx of research and prospective on concepts and processes pertaining previously to the Data Warehouse field. Some conclude that Data Warehouse as such will disappear; others present Big Data as the natural Data Warehouse evolution (perhaps without identifying a clear division between the two); and finally, some others pose a future of convergence, partially exploring the possible integration of both. In this paper, we revise the underlying technological features of Big Data and Data Warehouse, highlighting their differences and areas of convergence. Even when some differences exist, both technologies could (and should) be integrated because they both aim at the same purpose: data exploration and decision making support. We explore some convergence strategies, based on the common elements in both technologies. We present a revision of the state-of-the-art in integration proposals from the point of view of the purpose, methodology, architecture and underlying technology, highlighting the common elements that support both technologies that may serve as a starting point for full integration and we propose a proposal of integration between the two technologies.

KEYWORDS

Big Data, Data Warehouse, Integration, Hadoop, NoSql, MapReduce, 7V's, 3C's, M&G

For More Details: <https://airconline.com/ijcsit/V9N2/9217ijcsit01.pdf>

Volume Link: http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2017_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Bedi, V. Jindal, and A. Gautam, "[Beginning with Big Data Simplified](#)," 2014.
- [2] R. Kimball, M. Ross, W. Thorthwaite, B. Becker, and M. J., *The Data Warehouse Lifecycle Toolkit*, 2nd Edition. 2008.
- [3] C. Todman, *Designing A Data Warehouse: Supporting Customer Relationship Management*. 2001.
- [4] . H. Inmon, *Building the Data Warehouse*, 4th Edition. 2005.
- [5] "Oracle Database 12c for Data Warehousing and Big Data ." [Online]. Available: <http://www.oracle.com/technetwork/database/bi-datawarehousing/data-warehousing-wp-12c1896097.pdf>. [Accessed: 09-Sep-2015].
- [6] M. Cox and D. Ellsworth, "Application-Controlled Demand Paging for Out-of-Core Visualization," 1997. [Online]. Available: <http://www.nas.nasa.gov/assets/pdf/techreports/1997/nas-97-010.pdf>. [Accessed: 09-Apr-2015].
- [7] S. Chaudhuri and U. Dayal, "[An overview of data warehousing and OLAP technology](#)," *ACM SIGMOD Rec.*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 65–74, 1997.
- [8] T. Maiorescu, "General Information on Business Intelligence," pp. 294–297, 2010.
- [9] "Data Warehouses and OLAP: Concepts, Architectures and Solutions: 9781599043647: Library and Information Science Books | IGI Global." .
- [10] Y. Demchenko, C. De Laat, and P. Membrey, "Defining Architecture Components of the Big Data Ecosystem," *Collab. Technol. Syst. (CTS)*, 2014 Int. Conf., pp. 104–112, 2014.
- [11] G. NBD-PWG, "ISO/IEC JTC 1 Study Group on Big Data," 2013. [Online]. Available: <http://bigdatawg.nist.gov/cochairs.php>. [Accessed: 24-Oct-2015].
- [12] D. L. W.H. Inmon, *Data Architecture: A Primer for the Data Scientist: Big Data, Data Warehouse and Data Vault*. Amsterdam,Boston: Elsevier, 2014.
- [13] G. N. W.H. Inmon, Derek Strauss, *DW 2.0: The Architecture for the Next Generation of Data Warehousing (Morgan Kaufman Series in Data Management Systems) ()*: : Books. Burlington, USA: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc., 2008.
- [14] R. Kimball, "[The Evolving Role of the Enterprise Data Warehouse in the Era of Big Data Analytics](#)," Kimball Gr., 2011.
- [15] M. Muntean and T. Surcel, "Agile BI - The Future of BI," *Inform. Econ.*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 114–124, 2013.
- [16] D. Agrawal, "[The Reality of Real-Time Business Intelligence](#)," in *Business Intelligence for the RealTime Enterprise*, vol. 27 , M. Castellanos, U. Dayal, and T. Sellis, Eds. Springer Berlin Heidelberg , 2009, pp. 75–88.
- [17] R. Castillo, J. Morata, and L. del Arbol, "[Operational Data Store \(ODS\) - 933.pdf](#)," *Actas del III taller nacional de minería de datos y aprendizaje*, pp. 359–365, 2005.

- [18] S. YiChuan and X. Yao, "[Research of Real-time Data Warehouse Storage Strategy Based on Multilevel Caches](#)," Phys. Procedia, vol. 25, no. 0, pp. 2315–2321, 2012.
- [19] A. Ma. P. Díaz-zorita, "[Evaluación de la herramienta de código libre Apache Hadoop](#)," Universidad Carlos III de Madrid Escuela Politécnica Superior, 2011.
- [20] R. Kimball, "[Newly Emerging Best Practices for Big Data](#)," Kimball Group, p. 14, 2012.
- [21] M. Maier, "Towards a Big Data Reference Architecture," no. October, pp. 1–144, 2013.
- [22] O. Corporation, "ORACLE ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE WHITE PAPER. An Enterprise Architect's Guide to Big Data," no. February, 2015.
- [23] F. Kramer, H. Muller, and K. Turowski, "[Acceleration of Single Inserts for Columnar Databases -- An Experiment on Data Import Performance Using SAP HANA](#)," in Signal-Image Technology and Internet-Based Systems (SITIS), 2014 Tenth International Conference on, 2014, pp. 672–676.
- [24] M. R. Patil and F. Thia, Pentaho for Big Data Analytics, vol. 2013. PACKT PUBLISHING, 2013.
- [25] S. G. Manikandan and S. Ravi, "[Big Data Analysis Using Apache Hadoop](#)," in IT Convergence and Security (ICITCS), 2014 International Conference on, 2014, pp. 1–4.
- [26] J. Nandimath, E. Banerjee, A. Patil, P. Kakade, and S. Vaidya, "[Big data analysis using Apache Hadoop](#)," 2013 IEEE 14th Int. Conf. Inf. Reuse Integr., pp. 700–703, 2013.
- [27] A. Katal, M. Wazid, and R. H. Goudar, "[Big data: Issues, challenges, tools and Good practices](#)," in Contemporary Computing (IC3), 2013 Sixth International Conference on, 2013, pp. 404–409.
- [28] A. Pal and S. Agrawal, "[An Experimental Approach Towards Big Data for Analyzing Memory Utilization on a Hadoop cluster using HDFS and MapReduce .](#)," pp. 442–447, 2014.
- [29] R. Zhang, D. Hildebrand, and R. Tewari, "[In unity there is strength: Showcasing a unified big data platform with MapReduce Over both object and file storage](#)," in Big Data (Big Data), 2014 IEEE International Conference on, 2014, pp. 960–966.
- [30] "Welcome to Apache™ Hadoop®!" [Online]. Available: <https://hadoop.apache.org/> [Accessed: 26- Mar-2015].
- [31] "HDFS Architecture Guide." [Online]. Available: http://hadoop.apache.org/docs/r1.2.1/hdfs_design.html. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [32] S. Brin and L. Page, "The Anatomy of a Large-Scale Hypertextual Web Search Engine," in Computer Networks and ISDN Systems, 1998, pp. 107–117.
- [33] D. Garlasu, V. Sandulescu, I. Halcu, G. Neculoiu, O. Grigoriu, M. Marinescu, and V. Marinescu, "A big data implementation based on Grid computing," in Roedunet International Conference (RoEduNet), 2013 11th, 2013, pp. 1–4.
- [34] A. Jorgensen, C. Price, B. Mitchell, and J. Rowlan, Microsoft Big Data Solutions. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2014.

- [35] R. T. Kaushik, M. Bhandarkar, and K. Nahrstedt, "Evaluation and Analysis of GreenHDFS: A SelfAdaptive, Energy-Conserving Variant of the Hadoop Distributed File System," in Cloud Computing Technology and Science (CloudCom), 2010 IEEE Second International Conference on, 2010, pp. 274–287.
- [36] J. G. Shanahan and L. Dai, "Large Scale Distributed Data Science Using Apache Spark," in Proceedings of the 21th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, 2015, pp. 2323–2324.
- [37] R. S. Xin, J. Rosen, M. Zaharia, M. J. Franklin, S. Shenker, and I. Stoica, "Shark: SQL and Rich Analytics at Scale," in Proceedings of the 2013 ACM SIGMOD International Conference on Management of Data, 2013, pp. 13–24.
- [38] J. Li, J. Wu, X. Yang, and S. Zhong, "[Optimizing MapReduce Based on Locality of K-V Pairs and Overlap between Shuffle and Local Reduce](#)," in Parallel Processing (ICPP), 2015 44th International Conference on, 2015, pp. 939–948.
- [39] E. Brewer, "CAP Twelve Years Later: How the 'Rules' Have Changed," InfoQ, 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://www.infoq.com/articles/cap-twelve-years-later-how-the-rules-have-changed>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [40] G. Vaish, Getting started with NoSQL. 2013.
- [41] V. N. Gudivada, D. Rao, and V. V. Raghavan, "NoSQL Systems for Big Data Management," 2014 IEEE World Congr. Serv., pp. 190–197, 2014.
- [42] Cassandra, "The Apache Cassandra Project," <http://cassandra.apache.org>, 2010. [Online]. Available: <http://cassandra.apache.org/>.
- [43] D. Borthakur, "Petabyte Scale Databases and Storage Systems at Facebook," in Proceedings of the 2013 ACM SIGMOD International Conference on Management of Data, 2013, pp. 1267–1268.
- [44] J. Huang, X. Ouyang, J. Jose, M. Wasi-ur-Rahman, H. Wang, M. Luo, H. Subramoni, C. Murthy, and D. K. Panda, "High-Performance Design of HBase with RDMA over InfiniBand," in Parallel Distributed Processing Symposium (IPDPS), 2012 IEEE 26th International, 2012, pp. 774–785.
- [45] G. Weintraub, "[Dynamo and BigTable - Review and comparison](#)," Electr. Electron. Eng. Isr. (IEEEI), 2014 IEEE 28th Conv., pp. 1–5, 2014.
- [46] D. Pereira, P. Oliveira, and F. Rodrigues, "[Data warehouses in MongoDB vs SQL Server: A comparative analysis of the querie performance](#)," in Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI), 2015 10th Iberian Conference on, 2015, pp. 1–7.
- [47] K. Dehdouh, F. Bentayeb, O. Boussaid, and N. Kabachi, "Columnar NoSQL CUBE: Agregation operator for columnar NoSQL data warehouse," in Systems, Man and Cybernetics (SMC), 2014 IEEE International Conference on, 2014, pp. 3828–3833.
- [48] Y. Liu and T. M. Vitolo, "Graph Data Warehouse: Steps to Integrating Graph Databases Into the Traditional Conceptual Structure of a Data Warehouse," in Big Data (BigData Congress), 2013 IEEE International Congress on, 2013, pp. 433–434.
- [49] M. Chevalier, M. El Malki, A. Kopluku, O. Teste, and R. Tournier, "Benchmark for OLAP on NoSQL technologies comparing NoSQL multidimensional data warehousing solutions,"

in Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS), 2015 IEEE 9th International Conference on, 2015, pp. 480–485.

- [50] F. Färber, S. K. Cha, J. Primsch, C. Bornhövd, S. Sigg, and W. Lehner, “[SAP HANA Database: Data Management for Modern Business Applications](#),” SIGMOD Rec., vol. 40, no. 4, pp. 45–51, 2012.
- [51] K. M. A. Hasan, M. T. Omar, S. M. M. Ahsan, and N. Nahar, “[Chunking implementation of extendible array to handle address space overflow for large multidimensional data sets](#),” in Electrical Information and Communication Technology (EICT), 2013 International Conference on, 2014, pp. 1–6.
- [52] S. Müller and H. Plattner, “[An In-depth Analysis of Data Aggregation Cost Factors in a Columnar Inmemory Database](#),” in Proceedings of the Fifteenth International Workshop on Data Warehousing and OLAP, 2012, pp. 65–72.
- [53] H. Plattner, “A Common Database Approach for OLTP and OLAP Using an In-memory Column Database,” in Proceedings of the 2009 ACM SIGMOD International Conference on Management of Data, 2009, pp. 1–2.
- [54] J. Schaffner, A. Bog, J. Krüger, and A. Zeier, “[A Hybrid Row-Column OLTP Database Architecture for Operational Reporting](#),” in Business Intelligence for the Real-Time Enterprise SE - 5, vol. 27, M. Castellanos, U. Dayal, and T. Sellis, Eds. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2009, pp. 61–74.
- [55] V. K. Vavilapalli, A. C. Murthy, C. Douglas, S. Agarwal, M. Konar, R. Evans, T. Graves, J. Lowe, H. Shah, S. Seth, B. Saha, C. Curino, O. O’Malley, S. Radia, B. Reed, and E. Baldeschwieler, “Apache Hadoop YARN: Yet Another Resource Negotiator,” in Proceedings of the 4th Annual Symposium on Cloud Computing, 2013, pp. 5:1–5:16.
- [56] “Apache Pig Philosophy.” [Online]. Available: <http://pig.apache.org/philosophy.html>. [Accessed: 26- Mar-2015].
- [57] “Architecture - Apache Drill.” [Online]. Available: <http://drill.apache.org/architecture/>[Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [58] “Storm, distributed and fault-tolerant realtime computation.” [Online]. Available: <https://storm.apache.org/>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [59] “Apache Hive TM.” [Online]. Available: <https://hive.apache.org/>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [60] “Sqoop -.” [Online]. Available: <http://sqoop.apache.org/>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [61] “Impala.” [Online]. Available: <http://www.cloudera.com/content/cloudera/en/products-and-services/cdh/impala.html>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [62] “Apache Thrift - Home.” [Online]. Available: <https://thrift.apache.org/>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [63] “Apache ZooKeeper - Home.” [Online]. Available: <https://zookeeper.apache.org/>. [Accessed: 26- Mar-2015].
- [64] D. Borthakur, J. Gray, J. Sen Sarma, K. Muthukkaruppan, N. Spiegelberg, H. Kuang, K. Ranganathan, D. Molkov, A. Menon, S. Rash, R. Schmidt, and A. Aiyer, “Apache Hadoop Goes Realtime at Facebook,” in Proceedings of the 2011 ACM SIGMOD International

Conference on Management of Data, 2011, pp. 1071–1080.

- [65] B. Ghit, A. Iosup, and D. Epema, "[Towards an Optimized Big Data Processing System](#)," in Cluster, Cloud and Grid Computing (CCGrid), 2013 13th IEEE/ACM International Symposium on, 2013, pp. 83–86.
- [66] P. Agarwal, G. Shroff, and P. Malhotra, "[Approximate Incremental Big-Data Harmonization](#)," in Big Data (BigData Congress), 2013 IEEE International Congress on, 2013, pp. 118–125.
- [67] Y. Elshater, P. Martin, D. Rope, M. McRoberts, and C. Statchuk, "A Study of Data Locality in YARN," 2015 IEEE Int. Congr. Big Data, pp. 174–181, 2015.
- [68] A. H. B. James Manyika, Michael Chui, Brad Brown, Jacques Bughin, Richard Dobbs, Charles Roxburgh, "Big data: The next frontier for innovation, competition, and productivity," McKinsey Glob. Inst., no. June, p. 156, 2011.
- [69] J. S. Marron, "Big Data in context and robustness against heterogeneity," *Econom. Stat.*, vol. 2, pp. 73–80, 2017.
- [70] L. Kugler, "What Happens When Big Data Blunders?," *Commun. ACM*, vol. 59, no. 6, pp. 15–16, 2016.
- [71] S. Sagiroglu, R. Terzi, Y. Canbay, and I. Colak, "Big data issues in smart grid systems," in 2016 IEEE International Conference on Renewable Energy Research and Applications (ICRERA), 2016, pp. 1007–1012.
- [72] A. Gandomi and M. Haider, "[Beyond the hype: Big data concepts, methods, and analytics](#)," *Int. J. Inf. Manage.*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 137–144, 2015.
- [73] Jameela Al-Jaroodi, Brandon Hollein, Nader Mohamed, "[Applying software engineering rocesses for big data analytics applications development](#)", Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC) 2017 IEEE 7th Annual, pp. 1-7, 2017

THE SMART PARKING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Amira. A. Elsonbaty¹ and Mahmoud Shams²

¹Department of communication and electronics, Higher institute of engineering and technology, new Damietta, New Damietta, Egypt, 34517

²Department of Machine Learning and Information Retrieval, Faculty of Artificial Intelligence, Kafrelsheikh University, Kafrelsheikh, Egypt, 33511

ABSTRACT

With growing, Car parking increases with the number of car users. With the increased use of smartphones and their applications, users prefer mobile phone-based solutions. This paper proposes the Smart Parking Management System (SPMS) that depends on Arduino parts, Android applications, and based on IoT. This gave the client the ability to check available parking spaces and reserve a parking spot. IR sensors are utilized to know if a car park space is allowed. Its area data are transmitted using the WI-FI module to the server and are recovered by the mobile application which offers many options attractively and with no cost to users and lets the user check reservation details. With IoT technology, the smart parking system can be connected wirelessly to easily track available locations.

KEYWORDS

Internet of Things, Cloud Computing, Smart Parking, Smart City, Mobile Application.

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V12N4/12420ijcsit05.pdf>

Volume Link: http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2020_curr.html

REFERENCES

1. Abhirup Khanna, Rishi Anand, "IoT based Smart Parking System", Proc., In 2016 International Conference on Internet of Things and Applications (IOTA), 22 Jan - 24 Jan 2016.
2. Anusha, Arshitha M, S, Anushri, Geetanjali Bishtannavar "Review Paper on Smart Parking System," International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT), ISSN: 2278-0181, Volume 7, Issue 08, Special Issue – 2019.
3. S. Senthil, M. Suguna, J. Cynthia, "Mapping the Vegetation Soil and Water Region Analysis of Tuticorin District Using Landsat Images", IJEST ISSN (2455-8494), Vol.03, No. 01, Jan 2018.
4. Juhi Seth, Pola Ashritha, R Namith, "Smart Parking System using IoT ElakyaR", International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT), ISSN: 2249 – 8958, Volume-9 Issue-1, October 2019.
5. Mimbela, L.Y. and L.A. Klein, "A summary of vehicle detection and surveillance technologies used in intelligent transportation systems", New Mexico State University, Tech. The report, 2007.
6. M. Y. I. Idris, Y. Y. Leon, E. M. Tamil, N. M. Noor, and Z. Razak, "Car parking system: A review of the smart parking system and its technology," Information Technology Journal, pp. 101-113., 2009.
7. Paidi. V; Fleyeh, H.; Hakansson, J.; Nyberg, R.G., "Smart Parking Sensors, Technologies and Applications for Open Parking Lots: A Review", IET Intel. Transport Syst, 12, 735–741, 2018.
8. Amir O. Kotb, Yao-Chunsheng, and Yi Huang "Smart parking Guidance, Monitoring and Reservation: A Review," IEEE-ITSM, pp.6-16. Apr-2017.
9. Supriya Shinde, AnkitaM Patial, pSusmedha Chavan, Sayali Deshmukh, and Subodh Ingleshwar, "IOT Based Parking System Using Google", Proc., of. I-SMAC,2017, pp.634-636, 2017.
10. Hemant Chaudhary, PrateekBansal., B. Valarmathi," Advanced CAR Parking System using Arduino", Proc., of. ICACSS, 2017.
11. Wang, M.; Dong, H.; Li, X.; Song, L.; Pang, D. A Novel Parking System Designed for G. Searching page for parking H. View slots of parking Smart Cities. Proc., in 2017 Chinese Automation Congress (CAC), Jinan, China, pp. 3429–3434, 20–22 October 2017.
12. Nastaran Reza NazarZadeh, Jennifer C. Dela," Smart urban parking deducting system", Proc., of. ICSCE, 2016, pp-370-373,2016.
13. PavanKumarJogada and VinayakWarad, "Effective Car Parking Reservation System Based on Internet of things Technologies ", Proc., of. BIJSESC, Vol. 6, pp.140-142, 2016.
14. Yashomati R. Dhumal, Harshala A. Waghmare, Aishwarya S. Tole, Swati R. Shilimkar," Android Based Smart Car Parking System" Proc., of. IJREEIE, Vol. 5, Issue 3, pp-1371-74, mar-2016.
15. Faiz Ibrahim Shaikh, Pratik NirnayJadhav, Saideep Pradeep Bandarakar" Smart Parking System based on embedded system and sensor Network" IJCA, vol.140. pp.45-51. Apr-2016.
16. RicardGarra, Santi Martinez, and Francesc Seb"e" A Privacy-Preserving Pay-by-phone Parking system" IEEE-TVT, pp.1-10, Dec-2016.
17. Khanna, A.; Anand, R.," IoT based Smart Parking System", proc., in 2016 International Conference on Internet of Things and Applications (IOTA), Pune, India, 22–24 January 2016; pp. 266–270.
18. Karthi, M.; Preethi, H. Smart Parking with Reservation in Cloud-based environment. In Proceedings of the 2016 IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing in Emerging Markets, Bangalore, India, 19–21 October 2016; pp. 164–167.
19. Orrie, O.; Silva, B.; Hancke, G.P. "A Wireless Smart Parking System", proco., in 41st Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society (IECON), Yokohama, Japan, pp. 4110–4114, 9–12 November 2015.
20. Hsu, C.W.; Shih, M.H.; Huang, H.Y.; Shiue, Y.C.; Huang, S.C., "Verification of Smart Guiding System to Search for Parking Space via DSRC Communication", Proc., in 12th International Conference on ITS Telecommunications, Taipei, Taiwan, pp. 77–81, 5–8 November 2012.
21. Revathi, G., & Dhulipala," Smart parking systems and sensors: A survey", proc., in 2012 International Conference on Computing, Communication, and Applications, 2012.
22. Abhirup Khanna, Rishi Anand," IoT based Smart Parking System", proc., in International Conference on Internet of Things and Applications (IOTA) Maharashtra Institute of Technology, Pune, India 22 Jan - 24 Jan 2016.
23. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MQTT>, 18-7-2020.
24. Thusoo, A.; Sarma, J.S.; Jain, N.; Shao, Z.; Chakka, P.; Zhang, N.; Antony, S.; Liu, H.; Murthy, R. HIVE-A,"petabyte-scale data warehouse using Hadoop", proc., In 2010 IEEE 26th International Conference on Data Engineering (ICDE 2010), 2010.
25. <https://www.arduino.cc>, 18-7-2020.
26. ElakyaR, Juhi Seth, Pola Ashritha, R Namith," Smart Parking System using IoT ", International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT) ISSN: 2249 – 8958, Volume-9 Issue-1, October 2019.
27. <https://store.fut-electronics.com,18-7-2020>.

28. <https://www.instructables.com>, 18-7-2020.
29. <https://components101.com/sensors/tcrt5000-ir-sensor-pinout-datasheet>. 18-7-2020.
30. <https://engineering.eckovation.com>, 18-7-2020.
31. <https://www.variohm.com>, 18-7-2020.

QUERY OPTIMIZATION FOR BIG DATA ANALYTICS

Manoj Muniswamaiah, Tilak Agerwala and Charles Tappert

Seidenberg School of CSIS, Pace University, White Plains, New York

ABSTRACT

Organizations adopt different databases for big data which is huge in volume and have different data models. Querying big data is challenging yet crucial for any business. The data warehouses traditionally built with On-line Transaction Processing (OLTP) centric technologies must be modernized to scale to the ever-growing demand of data. With rapid change in requirements it is important to have near real time response from the big data gathered so that business decisions needed to address new challenges can be made in a timely manner. The main focus of our research is to improve the performance of query execution for big data.

KEYWORDS

Databases, Big data, Optimization, Analytical Query, Data Analysts and Data Scientists

For More Details: <http://aireconline.com/ijcsit/V11N5/11519ijcsit06.pdf>

Volume Link: http://aircse.org/journal/ijcsit2019_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Duggan, J., Elmore, A. J., Stonebraker, M., Balazinska, M., Howe, B., Kepner, J., et al. (2015). The BigDAWG Polystore System. *ACM Sigmod Record*, 44(3)
- [2] V. Srinivasan and M. Carey. Performance of B-Tree Concurrency Control Algorithms. In *Proc.ACM SIGMOD Conf.*, pages 416–425, 1991
- [3] A. Elmore, J. Duggan, M. Stonebraker, M. Balazinska, U. Cetintemel, V. Gadepally, J. Heer, B. Howe, J. Kepner, T. Kraska et al., “A demonstration of the bigdawg polystore system,” *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment*, vol. 8, no. 12, pp. 1908–1911, 2015
- [4] <http://kylin.apache.org>
- [5] D. Halperin et al. Demonstration of the myria big data management service. In *SIGMOD*, pages 881–884, 2014.
- [6] Fuad, A., Erwin, A. and Ipung, H.P., 2014, September. Processing performance on Apache Pig, Apache Hive and MySQL cluster. In *Information, Communication Technology and System (ICTS), 2014 International Conference on* (pp. 297-302). IEEE.
- [7] Liu, Shaosu, et al. "Kodiak: leveraging materialized views for very low-latency analytics over high-dimensional web-scale data." *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment* 9.13 (2016): 1269-1280
- [8] <https://lens.apache.org/>
- [9] <https://calcite.apache.org/>
- [10] Muniswamaiah, Manoj & Agerwala, Tilak & Tappert, Charles. (2019). Query Performance Optimization in Databases for Big Data. 85-90. 10.5121/csit.2019.90908.
- [11] <https://www1.nyc.gov/site/tlc/about/tlc-trip-record-data.page>
- [12] Luke Welling, Laura Thomson, *PHP and MySQL Web Development*, Sams, Indianapolis, IN, 2001
- [13] <https://www.spllicemachine.com/>
- [14] C. Bear, A. Lamb, and N. Tran. The vertica database: Sql rdbms for managing big data. In *Proceedings of the 2012 workshop on Management of big data systems*, pages 37–38. ACM, 2012
- [15] Cong Jin, Shuang Ran, "The research for storage scheme based on Hadoop", *Computer and Communications (ICCC) 2015 IEEE International Conference on*, pp. 62-66, 2015.

BIG DATA IN CLOUD COMPUTING REVIEW AND OPPORTUNITIES

**Manoj Muniswamaiah, Tilak Agerwala and Charles Tappert
Seidenberg School of CSIS, Pace University, White Plains, New York**

ABSTRACT

Big Data is used in decision making process to gain useful insights hidden in the data for business and engineering. At the same time it presents challenges in processing, cloud computing has helped in advancement of big data by providing computational, networking and storage capacity. This paper presents the review, opportunities and challenges of transforming big data using cloud computing resources.

KEYWORDS

Big data; cloud computing; analytics; database; data warehouse

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V11N4/11419ijcsit04.pdf>

Volume Link: http://aircse.org/journal/ijcsit2019_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Konstantinou, I., Angelou, E., Boumpouka, C., Tsoumakos, D., & Koziris, N. (2011, October). [On the elasticity of nosql databases over cloud management platforms](#). In Proceedings of the 20th ACM international conference on Information and knowledge management (pp. 2385-2388). ACM.
- [2] Labrinidis, Alexandros, and Hosagrahar V. Jagadish. "[Challenges and opportunities with big data](#)." Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment 5.12 (2012): 2032-2033.
- [3] Abadi, D. J. (2009). Data management in the cloud: Limitations and opportunities. IEEE Data Eng. Bull, 32(1), 3-12.
- [4] Luhn, H. P. (1958). A business intelligence system. IBM Journal of Research and Development, 2(4), 314-319
- [5] Sivarajah, Uthayasankar, et al. "[Critical analysis of Big Data challenges and analytical methods](#)." Journal of Business Research 70 (2017): 263-286.
- [6] <https://www.bmc.com/blogs/saas-vs-paas-vs-iaas-whats-the-difference-and-how-to-choose/>
- [7] Kavis, Michael J. Architecting the cloud: design decisions for cloud computing service models (SaaS, PaaS, and IaaS). John Wiley & Sons, 2014.
- [8] https://www.ripublication.com/ijaer17/ijaerv12n17_89.pdf
- [9] Sakr, S. & Gaber, M.M., 2014. Large Scale and big data: Processing and Management Auerbach, ed.
- [10] Ji, Changqing, et al. "Big data processing in cloud computing environments." 2012 12th international symposium on pervasive systems, algorithms and networks. IEEE, 2012.
- [11] Han, J., Haihong, E., Le, G., & Du, J. (2011, October). Survey on nosql database. In Pervasive Computing and Applications (ICPCA), 2011 6th International Conference on (pp. 363-366). IEEE.
- [12] Zhang, L. et al., 2013. Moving big data to the cloud. INFOCOM, 2013 Proceedings IEEE, pp.405-409
- [13] Fernández, Alberto, et al. "[Big Data with Cloud Computing: an insight on the computing environment, MapReduce, and programming frameworks](#)." Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery 4.5 (2014): 380-409.
- [14] http://acme.able.cs.cmu.edu/pubs/uploads/pdf/IoTBD_2016_10.pdf
- [15] Xiaofeng, Meng, and Chi Xiang. "[Big data management: concepts, techniques and challenges \[J\]](#)." Journal of computer research and development 1.98 (2013): 146-169.
- [16] Muniswamaiah, Manoj & Agerwala, Tilak & Tappert, Charles. (2019). [Challenges of Big Data Applications in Cloud Computing](#). 221-232. 10.5121/csit.2019.90918.

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF LTE NETWORK USING MAXIMUM FLOW ALGORITHM

Bir Bahadur Khatri¹, Bulbul Ahammad¹, Md. Mezbahul Islam², Rahmina Rubaiat² and
Md. Imdadul Islam¹

¹Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Jahangirnagar University,
Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

²Department of Computer Science and Engineering, MBSTU, Tangail, Bangladesh

Abstract

In this paper, we propose a new traffic flow model of the Long Term Evaluation (LTE) network for the Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access Network (E-UTRAN). Here only one Evolve Node B (eNB) nearest to the Mobility Management Entity (MME) and Serving Gateway (S-GW) will use the S1 link to bridge the E-UTRAN and Evolved Packet Core (EPC). All the eNBs of a tracking area will be connected to each other by the X2 link. Determination of capacity of a links of such a network is a challenging job since each node offers its own traffic and at the same time conveys traffic of other nodes. In this paper, we apply maximum flow algorithm including superposition theorem to solve the traffic flow of radio network. Using the total flow per subcarrier, a new traffic model is also developed in the paper. The relation among the traffic parameters: 'blocking probability', 'offered traffic', 'instantaneous capacity', 'average holding time', and 'number of users' are shown graphically under both QPSK and 16-QAM. The concept of the network will be helpful to improve the SINR of the received signal of eNBs located long distance relative to MME/S-GW.

Keywords

Aggregate offered traffic, blocking probability, traffic channel, weighted graph and RB.

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V12N4/12420ijcsit06.pdf>

Volume Link: http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2020_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Jesmin Akhter, Abu Sayed Md. MostafizurRahaman, Md. Imdadul Islam, M. R. Amin ‘Traffic Modelling of Low Dense Femtocellular Network for Long Term Evolution,’ *Journal of Computer and Communications*, pp.88-101, Vol.7, No.12, December 2019
- [2] Ma Lin, Wei Shouming and Qiang Wei, ‘A Novel Traffic Analysis Method For PoC over LTE Based on Retrial Calling Model,’ 2011 6th International ICST Conference on Communications and Networking in China (CHINACOM), 17-19 Aug. 2011, pp.771-774, Harbin, China
- [3] H. Hidayat, Al KautsarPermana, I. Ridwany, and Iskandar, ‘Cell Capacity Prediction with Traffic Load Effect for Soft Frequency Reuse (SFR) Technique in LTE – A Network,’ *The 11th International Conference on Telecommunication Systems, Services, and Applications*, 26-27 Oct. 2017, 26-27 October 2017, Lombok-Indonesia
- [4] Haka, V. Aleksieva and H. Valchanov, ‘Comparative Analysis of Traffic Prioritisation Algorithms by LTE Base Station Scheduler,’ *2020 21st International Symposium on Electrical Apparatus & Technologies (SIELA)*, pp. 1-4, 3-6 June 2020, Bourgas, Bulgaria
- [5] M. Sahu, ‘Delay Jitter Analysis for Uplink Traffic in LTE Systems,’ *2019 11th International Conference on Communication Systems & Networks (COMSNETS)*, pp. 504-506, 7-11 Jan. 2019, Bengaluru, India
- [6] R. Liu, Q. Chen, G. Yu, G. Y. Li and Z. Ding, ‘Resource Management in LTE-U Systems: Past, Present, and Future,’ *IEEE Open Journal of Vehicular Technology*, vol. 1, pp. 1-17, Oct’ 2020
- [7] Bulbul Ahammad, Risala T. Khan and Md. Imdadul Islam, ‘WLAN-LTE Integrated Traffic Model under Unlicensed Spectrum,’ *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS)*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp.85-100, March 2019
- [8] Fatima Sapundzhi and MetodiPopstoilov, ‘C# implementation of the maximum flow problem,’ *2019 27th National Conference with International Participation (TELECOM)*, pp. 62-65,30-31 Oct. 2019, Sofia, Bulgaria
- [9] Y. Wang, J. Ling, S. Zhou, Y. Liu, W. Liao and B. Zhang, ‘A Study on Rapid Incremental Maximum Flow Algorithm in Dynamic Network,’ *2018 1st International Cognitive Cities Conference (IC3)*, pp. 7-11, 7-9 Aug. 2018, Okinawa, Japan
- [10] Jiyang Dong, Wei Li, CongboCai, Zhong Chen, ‘Draining Algorithm for the Maximum Flow Problem,’ 2009 International Conference on Communications and Mobile Computing, pp.197-200, 6-8 Jan. 2009, Yunnan, China
- [11] Ruipeng Bail ,HuiGuo, Zhenzhong Wang, Yanlong Zhang, Fan Zhang and Lei Chen, ‘FPGA Interconnect Resources Test Based on A Improved Ford-Fulkerson Algorithm,’ 2018 IEEE 4th Information Technology and Mechatronics Engineering Conference (ITOEC 2018), pp.251-258, 14-16 Dec. 2018, Chongqing, China
- [12] Jesmin Akhter, Md. Imdadul Islam, ASM M Rahaman and M R Amin, ‘Performance Evaluation of Femtocell Based LTE Network under the Concept of Cross-layer Optimization,’*International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security*, pp. 52-60, vol. 14, no. 7, July 2016
- [13] Jesmin Akhter, Md. Imdadul Islam, ASM M Rahaman and M R Amin, ‘The MIMO Performance of LTE Network under Rayleigh Fading Environment,’ *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security*, pp. 88-94, vol. 14, no. 8, August 2016
- [14] Lifeng Zhao and XiaowanMeng, ‘An Improved Algorithm for Solving Maximum Flow Problem,’ 2012 8th International Conference on Natural Computation (ICNC 2012), pp.1016-1018, 29-31 May 2012, Chongqing, China
- [15] Bo Hong and Zhengyu He, ‘An Asynchronous Multithreaded Algorithm for the Maximum Network Flow Problem with Nonblocking Global Relabeling Heuristic,’ *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems*, pp.1025-1033, vol. 22, no. 6, June 2011
- [17] Ali Mustafa Elshawesh, Mohamed Abdulali, ‘Dimensioning of Circuit Switched Networks by using Simulation Code based on Erlang (B) formula,’ 2014 Global Summit on Computer & Information Technology (GSCIT), pp. 1-5, 14-16 June 2014, Sousse, Tunisia
- [17] James K. Tamgno, Mamadou Alpha Barry, Simplicie E. Gngang, Claude Lishou, ‘Estimating Number of Organs using Erlang’s B & C-Formulas,’2017 19th International Conference on Advanced Communication Technology (ICTACT), pp.858-864, 19-22 Feb. 2017, Bongpyeong, South Korea

AUTHORS

Birbahadur Khatri completed his B.Sc. in Computer Science and Engineering from Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka in 2015 and M.Sc. in the same discipline from the same University in 2016. He worked as a programming trainer in Green University of Bangladesh and as a software engineer at Newscred in Bangladesh from 2017 to 2018. Currently, he is working as a software engineer at Google in UK since 2019. He has excellent computer programming problem solving skill. He took part in many competitive programming contests both onsite and online and has a very good contest rating in Codeforces. He is very enthusiastic at research work and his fields of interest are algorithm analysis and constructive algorithm design, wireless communication and machine learning.

Bulbul Ahammad completed his B.Sc. in Computer Science and Engineering from Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka in 2015 and M.Sc. in the same discipline from the same University in 2016. He worked as a lecturer at the department of Computer Science and Engineering in Daffodil International University from 1st January, 2017 to 24th June 2019. He has been at the Department of Computer Science and Engineering as a lecturer in Jahangirnagar University since 25th June, 2019. He took part in many competitive programming contests and has a very good skill in solving constructive computer programming problem. He has a great enthusiasm for innovative research work and his fields of research interest are machine learning, algorithm analysis and design, image processing and wireless communication.

Md. Mezbahul Islam received his B.Sc. (Honors) and M.Sc. in Computer Science and Engineering from Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh in 2015 and 2017 respectively. He has been working as a faculty in the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, MawlanaBhashani Science and Technology University, Tangail, Bangladesh since April 2017. His research is focused in the fields of Image Processing, Pattern Recognition, Wireless Network and Machine Learning.

RahminaRubaiat completed her B.Sc. (Honors) and M.Sc. in Computer Science and Engineering from Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh in 2015 and 2017 respectively. She worked as a faculty in the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Brac University, Dhaka, Bangladesh since October 2015 to June 2019. Currently, she is working as a faculty member in the department of Computer Science and Engineering, MawlanaBhashani Science and Technology University, Tangail, Bangladesh since June 2019. Her research focused in the fields of Image Processing, Data Science, Pattern Recognition and Wireless Network.

Md. Imdadul Islam has completed his B.Sc. and M.Sc Engineering in Electrical and Electronic Engineering from Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology, Dhaka, Bangladesh in 1993 and 1998 respectively and has completed his Ph.D degree from the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh in the field of network traffic in 2010. He is now working as a Professor at the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Previously, he worked as an Assistant Engineer in Sheba Telecom (Pvt.) LTD (A joint venture company between Bangladesh and Malaysia, for Mobile cellular and WLL), from Sept.1994 to July 1996. Dr Islam has a very good field experience in installation and design of mobile cellular network, Radio Base Stations and Switching Centers for both mobile and WLL. His research field is network traffic, wireless communications, wavelet transform, adaptive filter theory, ANFIS, neural network, deep learning and machine learning. He has more than hundred and eighty research papers in national and international journals and conference proceedings.

DATA MINING MODEL PERFORMANCE OF SALES PREDICTIVE ALGORITHMS BASED ON RAPIDMINER WORKFLOWS

Alessandro Massaro, Vincenzo Maritati, Angelo Galiano

**Dyrecta Lab, IT research Laboratory, via Vescovo Simplicio,
45, 70014 Conversano (BA), Italy**

ABSTRACT

By applying RapidMiner workflows has been processed a dataset originated from different data files, and containing information about the sales over three years of a large chain of retail stores. Subsequently, has been constructed a Deep Learning model performing a predictive algorithm suitable for sales forecasting. This model is based on artificial neural network –ANN- algorithm able to learn the model starting from sales historical data and by pre-processing the data. The best built model uses a multilayer eural network together with an “optimized operator” able to find automatically the best parameter setting of the implemented algorithm. In order to prove the best performing predictive model, other machine learning algorithms have been tested. The performance comparison has been performed between Support Vector Machine –SVM-, k-Nearest Neighbor k-NN-, Gradient Boosted Trees, Decision Trees, and Deep Learning algorithms. The comparison of the degree of correlation between real and predicted values, the verage absolute error and the relative average error proved that ANN exhibited the best performance. The Gradient Boosted Trees approach represents an alternative approach having the second best performance. The case of study has been developed within the framework of an industry project oriented on the integration of high performance data mining models able to predict sales using–ERP- and customer relationship management –CRM- tools.

KEYWORDS

RapidMiner, Neural Network, Deep Learning, Gradient Boosted Trees, Data Mining Performance, Sales Prediction.

For More Details : <http://aircconline.com/ijcsit/V10N3/10318ijcsit03.pdf>

Volume Link: http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2018_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Penpece D., & Elma O. E. (2014) "[Predicting Sales Revenue by Using Artificial Neural Network in Grocery Retailing Industry: A Case Study in Turkey](#)", International Journal of Trade Economics and Finance, Vol. 5, No. 5, pp435-440.
- [2] Thiesing F. M., & Vornberger, O. (1997) "[Sales Forecasting Using Neural Networks](#)", IEEE Proceedings ICNN'97, Houston, Texas, 9-12 June 1997, pp2125-2128.
- [3] Zhang, G. P. (2003) "[Time series forecasting using a hybrid ARIMA and neural network model](#)", Neurocomputing, Vol. 50, pp159–175.
- [4] Sharma, A., & Panigrahi, P. K. (2011) "[Neural Network based Approach for Predicting Customer Churn in Cellular Network Services](#)", International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 27, No.11, pp0975–8887.
- [5] Kamakura, W., Mela, C. F., Ansari A., & al. (2005) "[Choice Models and Customer Relationship Management](#)," Marketing Letters, Vol. 16, No.3/4, pp279–291.
- [6] Smith, K. A., & Gupta, J. N. D. (2000) "[Neural Networks in Business: Techniques and Applications for the Operations Researcher](#)," Computers & Operations Research, Vol. 27, No. 11–12, pp1023- 1044.
- [7] Chattopadhyay, M., Dan, P. K., Majumdar, S., & Chakraborty, P. S. (2012) "[Application of Artificial Neural Network in Market Segmentation: A Review on Recent Trends](#)," Management Science Letters, Vol. 2, pp425-438.
- [8] Berry, J. A. M., & Linoff, G. S. (2004) "[Data Mining Techniques For Marketing, Sales, and Customer Relationship Management](#)", Wiley, Second Edition.
- [9] Buttle, F. (2009) "[Customer Relationship Management Concepts and Technologies](#)", Elsevier, Second Edition.
- [10] Thomassey, S. (2014) "[Sales Forecasting in Apparel and Fashion Industry: A Review](#)", Springer, chapter 2.
- [11] Massaro, A. Barbuzzi, D., Vitti, V., Galiano, A., Aruci, M., Pirlo, G. (2016) "[Predictive Sales Analysis According to the Effect of Weather](#)", Proceeding of the 2nd International Conference on Recent Trends and Applications in Computer Science and Information Technology, Tirana, Albania, November 18 - 19, pp53-55.
- [12] Parsons, A.G. (2001), "[The Association between Daily Weather and Daily Shopping Patterns](#)", Australasian Marketing Journal, Vol. 9, No. 2, pp78–84.

- [13] Steele, A.T., (1951) "Weather's Effect on the Sales of a Department Store", Journal of Marketing Vol. 15, No. 4, pp436-443.
- [14] Murray, K. B., Di Muro, F., Finn, A., & Leszczyc, P. P. (2010) "[The Effect of Weather on Consumer Spending](#)", Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services, Vol. 17, No.6, pp512-520.
- [15] Massaro, A., Galiano, A., Barbuzzi, D., Pellicani, L., Birardi, G., Romagno, D. D., & Frulli, L., (2017) "[Joint Activities of Market Basket Analysis and Product Facing for Business Intelligence oriented on Global Distribution Market: examples of data mining applications](#)," International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies, Vol. 8, No.2 , pp178- 183.
- [16] Aguinis, H., Forcum, L. E., & Joo, H. (2013) "[Using Market Basket Analysis in Management Research](#)," Journal of Management, Vol. 39, No. 7, pp1799-1824.
- [17] Štulec, I, Petljak, K., & Kukor, A. (2016) "[The Role of Store Layout and Visual Merchandising in Food Retailing](#)", European Journal of Economics and Business Studies, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp139- 152.
- [18] Otha, M. & Higuci, Y. (2013) "Study on Design of Supermarket Store Layouts: the Principle of "Sales Magnet"", World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 7, No. 1, pp209-212.
- [19] Shallu, & Gupta, S. (2013) "[Impact of Promotional Activities on Consumer Buying Behavior: A Study of Cosmetic Industry](#)", International Journal of Commerce, Business and Management (IJCBM), Vol. 2, No.6, pp379-385.
- [20] Al Essa, A. & Bach, C. (2014)" [Data Mining and Knowledge Management for Marketing](#)", International Journal of Innovation and Scientific Research, Vol. 2, No. 2, pp321-328.
- [21] Kotu, V., & Deshpande B. (2015) "Predictive Analytics and Data Mining- Concepts and Practice with RapidMiner" Elsevier.
- [22] Wimmer, H., Powell, L. M. (2015) "[A Comparison of Open Source Tools for Data Science](#)", Proceedings of the Conference on Information Systems Applied Research. Wilmington, North Carolina USA.
- [23] Al-Khoder, A., Harmouch, H., "[Evaluating Four Of The most Popular Open Source and Free Data Mining Tools](#)", International Journal of Academic Scientific Research, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp13-23.

- [24] Gulli, A., & Pal, S. (2017) “Deep Learning with Keras- Implement neural networks with Keras on Theano and TensorFlow,” Birmingham -Mumbai Packt book, ISBN 978-1-78712-842-2.
- [25] Kovalev, V., Kalinovsky, A., & Kovalev, S. (2016) “[Deep Learning with Theano, Torch, Caffe, TensorFlow, and deeplearning4j: which one is the best in speed and accuracy?](#)” Proceeding of XIII Int. Conf. on Pattern Recognition and Information Processing, 3-5 October, Minsk, Belarus State University, pp99-103.

AUTHOR

Alessandro Massaro: Research & Development Chief of Dyrecta Lab s.r.l.

INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM CLASSIFICATION USING DIFFERENT MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS ON KDD-99 AND NSL-KDD DATASETS - A REVIEW PAPER

Ravipati Rama Devi¹ and Munther Abualkibash²

**¹Department of Computer Science, Eastern Michigan University,
Ypsilanti, Michigan, USA**

**²School of Information Security and Applied Computing, Eastern Michigan University,
Ypsilanti, Michigan, USA**

ABSTRACT

Intrusion Detection System (IDS) has been an effective way to achieve higher security in detecting malicious activities for the past couple of years. Anomaly detection is an intrusion detection system. Current anomaly detection is often associated with high false alarm rates and only moderate accuracy and detection rates because it's unable to detect all types of attacks correctly. An experiment is carried out to evaluate the performance of the different machine learning algorithms using KDD-99 Cup and NSL-KDD datasets. Results show which approach has performed better in term of accuracy, detection rate with reasonable false alarm rate.

..

KEYWORDS

Intrusion Detection System, KDD-99 cup, NSL-KDD, Machine learning algorithms.

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V11N3/11319ijcsit06.pdf>

Volume Link: http://aircse.org/journal/ijcsit2019_curr.html

